

Playing the Pinball game with Spiking Neural Networks

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Abstract Inspired by biological principles, we propose a neuromorphic model to control the timing of flipper activation in a pinball game. This task is particularly challenging due to the need for high temporal precision and accurate tracking of the ball's motion in the drain region between the two flippers. At the same time, it offers a valuable toy problem for exploring solutions to more complex real-time robotic challenges. Event-based cameras, combined with spiking neural networks (SNNs), provide distinct advantages over traditional artificial neural networks (ANNs) in such contexts. Unlike frame-based sensors, event-based cameras detect asynchronous changes in brightness at microsecond resolution, enabling low-latency, high-speed motion detection. SNNs process this data stream, preserving temporal dynamics and offering high energy efficiency. To detect the direction, speed, and position of the moving ball with millisecond latency, we draw inspiration from the MT/V5 area of the brain, which plays a central role in motion processing [1].

Methods Building on our previous work on coastline detection using SNNs on SpiNNaker [2], we introduce a neuromorphic processing pipeline for estimating the motion characteristics, direction, orientation, and speed of a moving ball in a pinball game. This system leverages Spiking Elementary Motion Detectors (sEMDs) [3], which encode traversal time between adjacent receptive fields as bursts of spikes, producing a spiking, asynchronous representation of motion. To enable precise ground-truth validation, we developed a custom simulator where the ball moves at predefined speeds. In the physical setup, an event-based camera captures the scene and transmits asynchronous spikes via Ethernet to the SpiNNaker board. Figure 1a shows the field of view segmented into orientation sectors, which are used to determine the ball's position and orientation relative to the left and right flippers. It also highlights the sEMD populations responsible for detecting motion direction (inward/outward). The spike activity, quantified by the mean firing rate (MFR) of the sEMD populations, provides actionable information for real-time decisions, such as triggering the appropriate flipper.

Preliminary Results We evaluated the model's ability to estimate the orientation, direction, and speed of a

Figure 1: a) Orientation-distance sectors centered on the left flipper with corresponding sEMD populations. b) Input speed of the ball moving outward from the right flipper. c) MFR across all output populations. d) MFR vs. average detected orientation.

moving ball. Four test scenarios were designed by combining flipper location (left/right) with motion direction (inward/outward). In each scenario, the ball moved at a constant speed ranging from 0 to 400 px/s over a 2 second interval. Figure 1b illustrates results for a representative case in which the ball moves outward from the right flipper. Figure 1c shows the MFR across all populations, grouped by direction (inward/outward) and flipper (left/right). The dominant activity in the right-outward group aligns with the simulated motion. Figure 1d shows the MFR of each orientation-selective population. Only the right-outward populations are active, with peak activity centred near the correct motion direction, indicating a straight trajectory. To assess the relationship between MFR and translational speed, we trained a regression model on the output of the direction-speed sEMD populations. The model achieved an R^2 of 0.894, with a relative MAE of 9.43% and an RMSE of 11.11%, confirming accurate speed prediction from spike dynamics. Each input spike reaches output neurons within 4 ms due to fixed synaptic connectivity. The overall response time depends on the MFR accumulation window, enabling latency tuning to meet specific application requirements. Our implementation employs 25,356 spiking neurons and maintains a 4ms system latency, supporting fast and precise motion estimation.

References

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